

New Synthesis of 2-Ethoxycarbonyl-Coumaran-3-one and its Alkylation in Polar and Nonpolar Solvent by Ethylchloro Formate

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In the course of other work we had the occasion to attempt the synthesis of substituted 2, 2-diethoxycarbonyl-coumaran-3-ones by the Dieckmann cyclisation of ethyl 2-ethoxycarbonyl-phenoxy-malonates. The attempt was unsuccessful and the reaction resulted in the formation of 2-ethoxycarbonyl-coumaran-3-one. The desired compound, however, was obtained by alkylating the potassium salt of 2-ethoxycarbonylcoumaran-3-one with ethylchloroformate.

Ethyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-4-bromophenoxy-malonate (I) was allowed to undergo intramolecular cyclization in presence of sodium methoxide in dry ether. 2-Ethoxycarbonyl-5-bromo-coumaran-3 one (III) was obtained by the extrusion of a molecule of ethyl-methylcarbonate instead of the expected Dieckmann product (II). The identity of (III), was established by a synthesis involving cyclisation of ethyl-4-bromo-2-methoxycarbonylphenoxyacetate (VI) in presence of pulverized sodium in dry xylene. The melting point, IR spectra ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1720 cm^{-1}) and the elemental analysis were identical.

The alkylation of 2-ethoxycarbonylcyclopentanone in polar and nonpolar solvents, using its sodium and potassium salts has been extensively studied^{1,2}. It has been reported²

1. S. J. Rhoads and R. W. Hasbrouck; *Tetrahedron*, 1966, **22**, 3557.

2. D. M. Pond and R. L. Cargill, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **32**, 4064.

that the alkylation of potassium salt of a β -ketoester in dimethylsulphoxide led to C-alkylation quantitatively. We have found that the interaction of the potassium salt of (III) with ethylchlorocarbonate in a polar solvent like acetonitrile at room temperature (25-30°) provides good yields (94%) of C-alkylated keto ester (II) which was exactly similar to the one prepared by alkylation of sodium salt of (III) in benzene. We were unable to detect any appreciable o-alkylated product in polar and nonpolar solvent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted phenoxy malonate³ (I) was prepared by refluxing until neutral, equimolar quantities of diethyl-monochloromalonate and substituted sodium phenolate (IV) in absolute ethanol. Dilution with water followed by the extraction with ether afforded (I) m.p. 45° in 60% yield. (I) with equimolar sodium methoxide was taken in dry ether, refluxed for 24 hr. with constant stirring and water was then added. On shaking vigorously with ether it gave ethylmethylcarbonate b.p. 105-6°; the aqueous phase neutralised with dilute acetic acid in cold and extracted with ether gave (III) m.p. 142°.

To alkylate (III), the sodium salt of 2-ethoxycarbonyl-coumaran-3-one isolated after Dieckmann cyclisation of (VI) was treated with ethylchloroformate in dry benzene under reflux for 1-2 hr. according to the method by Komppa⁴ to furnish (II), m.p. 91°.

The analytical values for elements in compounds (I), (II) and (III) corresponded with the formulae $C_{15}H_{17}O_7Br$, $C_{14}H_{13}O_6Br$ and $C_{11}H_9O_4Br$ respectively.

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3. J. B. Niederl and R. T. Roth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1154.
4. G. Komppa and A. Talvitie, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1944, **38**, 5496.